

A Model for Failure Mode and Effects Analysis based Single Valued Neutrosophic Sets

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Abstract: Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) is an effective risk management technique widely used for performance improvement and risk mitigation in various fields of industry and science. However, FMEA has been justifiably criticized for its many shortcomings and limitations. The current study proposed a novel model for FMEA based on single-valued neutrosophic (SVN) approach to overcome the shortcomings of classical FMEA in the area of risk prioritization. This approach offers advantages over previous models and provides a means to evaluate Failure modes (FMs), while dealing with vague concepts and insufficient data. In this approach, SVNSs are used to deal with the uncertainty and vagueness in information. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) that is integrated with SVNSs is used to determine the weight of risk factors for FMEA. In the end, risk items are ranked by SVN version of VIKOR (Vlsekriterijumska Optimizacija I Kompromisno Resenje) based on the obtained factor weights. To demonstrate its applicability, the method is applied to a case study of Iran Central Iron Ore Co. (ICIIOC) (Bafgh, Iran). The results indicate that the FMs of Sanctions, Price and cost fluctuations and Inflation and exchange rate changes are the most important in ICIIOC. As a result, this method helps to improve the performance of this company by identifying and prioritizing failure cases in conditions of ambiguity and uncertainty, which can be used in other industries as well.

Keywords: FMEA; Single-Valued Neutrosophic set (SVNS); AHP; VIKOR.

1. Introduction

Proper risk management is an essential requirement for the success of any undertaking and determines whether managers can mitigate foreseen and unforeseen risks in different aspects of their projects. This is why a great majority of businesses and organizations need to have some kind of risk assessment mechanism in place. One of the most widely known and accepted risk assessment methods is the FMEA [1]. Widely regarded as one of the best risk and reliability analysis methods, FMEA is commonly used to assess and rank the ways in which a process or system may fail. FMEA is extensively used in system safety engineering as an efficient qualitative analysis method. It was first developed by the U.S. military in the 1940s as a reliability analysis tool and then used by NASA [2] in the 1960s to improve the safety and quality of its projects. Following its inclusion in standards such as MIL-STD 1629A. FMEA became a method of choice for risk management in the industrial design of products such as aircraft engines, space vehicles, and marine vessels. FMEA is often used to detect modes of failure in complex systems in order to eradicate risk factors and improve product safety and reliability. The important goal of FMEA is to identify deficiencies in the product design

phase and analyze accordingly how each component may fail and how this failure can impact other components and the system as a whole [3]. FMEA is applicable in various fields, including supplier selection, marine engineering, and healthcare management. For example, FMEA has been used to detect failure in wind turbines, machinery industry, online banking, medical profession, geothermal power plants, paper industry and steam valve systems.

Classic FMEA is implemented in five stages including preparation, identification, prioritization, risk mitigation, and reassessment. In this version of FMEA, risk analysis is performed by a measure called Risk Priority Number (RPN), which is a numerical value reflecting the probability of Occurrence (O), the probability of Detection (D), and the Severity of impact (S) of a failure event [4]. To obtain RPN, each of the parameters O, D, and S is given a score on a scale of 1 to 10 (with 1 representing the best and 10 representing the worst condition), and these scores are multiplied together. The most important part of the risk mitigation process is to determine high-risk failure modes. Low-risk hazards tend to have little effect on processes and should therefore be placed at the bottom of the list of priorities [5]. Although the described RPN approach is a simple practical method for risk assessment and prioritization in FMEA, it has been widely criticized for its many shortcomings including the following [6, 7]: 1- it ignores the fact that S, O, and D may not be equally important for a process (lack of relative importance weights); 2- different combinations of S, O, and D may produce the same RPN while having significantly different risk implications; 3- RPN is obtained by simple multiplication of S, O and D, which is not sophisticated enough for critical risk assessment; 4- the mathematical formula of Risk Priority Number is highly sensitive to changes in its risk factors while completely ignoring other important risk factors such as expected cost (E); and 5- the opinions of experts are integrated in a very simplistic way, which can easily lead to data loss. Thus, conventional FMEA has to be improved into a more flexible tool for system safety and risk management.

Over the years, a number of improvements have been made in both the methodology and application of FMEA. These improvements include the introduction of the fuzzy set (FS) theory, specifically triangular fuzzy sets (TFSs), triangular interval-valued fuzzy sets (TIVFSs), interval type 2 fuzzy sets (IT2FSs), Pythagorean fuzzy sets (PFSs), gray fuzzy sets (GFSs), intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs), interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IVIFSs), and hesitant fuzzy sets (HFSs), and also other theories such as the D-numbers theory, prospect theory, and Dempster-Shafer evidence theory to FMEA. According to the aforementioned extensions, several studies have been conducted, including Zandi et al [8] on fuzzy FMEA in agricultural projects. Tian et al [9] investigated FMEA with triangular interval type-2 fuzzy (TIT2F) in a Chinese state-owned enterprise. Qin et al [10] overcome some of the disadvantages of the conventional FMEA approach and deal with uncertainties more effectively by combining IT2FSs and Evidential Reasoning. Rahnamay Bonab and Osgooei [11] assessed the environmental risk of wastewater treatment using the FMEA method based on PF Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM). Sayyadi Tooranloo et al [12] investigated FMEA in an IF environment in Khuzestan Oil and Gas Company.

There have also been many efforts to integrate MCDM methods into FMEA. The integration of FMEA with fuzzy logic eliminates many of its shortcomings and makes it work better with missing and insufficient data and vague concepts. But fuzzy logic has its own issues, primary among which is the time and resources required to build a complete set of rules before starting any inferential

process. Also, notwithstanding the method's ability to work with ambiguity and uncertainty, in a wide variety of complex situations, it is genuinely difficult to decide what exact values should be assigned to membership and non-membership degrees. Under such circumstances, it might be better to integrate NSs with FMEA. The fuzzy theory and the IFS both evolved into NSs, which are extensions of the two. Neutrosophic numbers (NNs) have established themselves as a legitimate area of research that may be used to recognize incongruous and ill-defined data [13].

The concept of NSs was first introduced by Smarandach for a better mathematical representation of uncertainty and vagueness that are typically present in real-world problems. A NS is characterized by three membership functions called truth (T) function, indeterminacy (I) function, and falsity (F) function. The use of three membership functions distinguishes NSs from Lotfizadeh's traditional FSs, which have a single membership function. Also, unlike IFSs, NSs make use of an I function representing the degree of uncertainty, which helps experts better express uncertainty and ambiguity in their opinions and also allows for a better representation of differences of opinion among decision-makers. Other features distinguishing NSs from IFSs include [14]: (1) The sum of the values of T, I and F parameters may be at most three and they can be independently assigned. (2) I value does not depend on the values of T and F parameters. (3) They extend decision makers disagreements. Since their appearance and the ability to tackle the I, they are frequently applied to hot topics to tackle the MCDM problems such as risk assessment [15].

According to the review of several studies, unfortunately, no previous studies have presented a model of FMEA based on SVN for risk assessment and ranking. So, Considering the merits of NSs, this paper presents a new FMEA incorporating a combination of the SVN version of VIKOR (SVNVIKOR) and the SVN version of AHP (SVNAHP) with the goal of avoiding certain shortcomings of traditional FMEA in the area of risk prioritization. Considering the inconsistent performance of VIKOR and AHP in dealing with the vagueness that is typically present in real-world problems, it was decided to use SVNVIKOR and SVNAHP jointly in FMEA. The proposed framework is applied under a Neutrosophic environment to ensure more accurate results and deal with uncertainty and vague conditions. To demonstrate its applicability, the method was used in a risk assessment conducted for ICIOC in Bafgh, Iran.

1.1. Contributions of This Study

According to the sources mentioned in the relevant research, The goal purpose of this study is to introduce a new FMEA based on SVN and AHP-VIKOR method for ranking FM_s in the ICIOC. in Bafgh, Iran. Based on this, the works of this article are as follows:

(i) This approach includes prioritizing failure items and identifying strategies that can be applied to deal with these risks. Also, the approach is divided into three stages: Determining the weight of experts; Determining the weight of risk factors in order to assess risks and determine the prioritization of failure items to prevent these risks. In this research, a system of realistic failure items was developed based on literature and expert opinions to provide a comprehensive assessment basis for identifying and prioritizing risks.

(ii) A new FMEA, with the SVNAHP-SVNVIKOR method, is discussed for ranking and prioritizing FM_s related to ICIOC. The weight of the risk factors are evaluated using the SVNAHP technique, and the FM_s are rated using the SVNVIKOR technique. The proposed approach uses the Neutrosophic weighted average operator with unit value to aggregate the matrices of pairwise comparisons of experts.

1.2. Structure of This Study

To accomplish our study objectives, the following segments of this paper are structured as follows: In Section 2, we concisely review some related definitions, then we construct the hybrid approach FMEA with SVN based on the AHP-VIKOR method. Section 3, Then the proposed approach of this research is shown as a diagram. Section 4 illustrates the evaluation process of ICIOC. in Bafgh, Iran risks. Finally, sensitivity analysis was performed to achieve the stability and validity of the proposed model. Section 5 provides a discussion related to the findings obtained from the application of the suggested approach. Some concluding remarks and future outlooks are certified at the end.

2. Methodology

This section starts with an introduction to the concept of SVN_Ss and then describes AHP, VIKOR, and their SVN versions.

2.1. Preliminaries on SVN_Ss

SVN_Ss are a sub-type of NSs. This section introduces the definition of these sets and the operations between them.

Definition 1. Supposing X is the reference set, the SVN_S A is characterized by a $T_A(x)$, an $I_A(x)$, and $F_A(x)$, and is denoted by $A = \{x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) | x \in X\}$ where $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ holds for any $x \in X$. Therefore, $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$ for any x [16]

Definition 2. Operations between the SVN_Ss $A = \langle T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$ and $B = \langle T_B(x), I_B(x), F_B(x) \rangle$ are defined in Eqs. (1-6) [17]:

$$A \oplus B = \left\{ \langle x, T_A(x) + T_B(x) - T_A(x) \cdot T_B(x), I_A(x) \cdot I_B(x), F_A(x) \cdot F_B(x) \rangle | x \in X \right\}. \tag{1}$$

$$A \otimes B = \{ \langle x, T_A(x) \cdot T_B(x), I_A(x) + I_B(x) - I_A(x) \cdot I_B(x), F_A(x) + F_B(x) - F_A(x) \cdot F_B(x) \rangle | x \in X \}. \tag{2}$$

$$A \cup B = \left\{ \langle x, \max(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \min(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle | x \in X \right\}. \tag{3}$$

$$A \cap B = \left\{ \langle x, \min(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \max(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle | x \in X \right\}. \tag{4}$$

$$\lambda \cdot A = \left\{ \langle x, 1 - (1 - T_A)^\lambda, I_A^\lambda, F_A^\lambda \rangle | x \in X \right\}, \quad \square \lambda > 0 \tag{5}$$

$$A^\lambda = \left\{ \langle x, T_A^\lambda(x), I_A^\lambda(x), F_A^\lambda(x) \rangle | x \in X \right\}, \quad \square \lambda > 0 \tag{6}$$

Definition 3. The complement of a SVN_S A is denoted by A^c and is defined in Eq. (7) [18].

$$A^c = \left\{ \langle x, F_A(x), 1 - I_A(x), T_A(x) \rangle | x \in X \right\}. \tag{7}$$

Definition 4. Supposing $A = (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n)$ and $B = (B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n)$ are two vectors comprised of n SVNNs where $A_j = \langle T_A(x_i), I_A(x_i), F_A(x_i) \rangle$ and $B_j = \langle T_B(x_i), I_B(x_i), F_B(x_i) \rangle$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), the normalized Euclidean distance between A and B is defined in Eq. (8) [19]:

$$E_N(A, B) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(|T_A(x_i) - T_B(x_i)|^2 + |I_A(x_i) - I_B(x_i)|^2 + |F_A(x_i) - F_B(x_i)|^2 \right)} \tag{8}$$

And the normalized Hamming distance between A and B is defined in Eq. (9):

$$L_{Ham(N)}(A, B) = \frac{1}{3n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(|T_A(x_i) - T_B(x_i)| + |I_A(x_i) - I_B(x_i)| + |F_A(x_i) - F_B(x_i)| \right) \tag{9}$$

Definition 5. Supposing $A = (T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x))$ is a SVNN, the score function of A , denoted by $S(A)$, is defined in Eq. (10) [20].

$$S(A) = \frac{3 + T_A(x) - 2I_A(x) - F_A(x)}{4}; S(A) \in [0, 1] \tag{10}$$

2.2. Steps of SVNAHP

AHP was first introduced by Thomas Saati in 1980 and over the years was integrated with FSs [21] and their extensions including TFSs, spherical fuzzy sets (SFSs), IT2FSs, IFSs, IVIFSs, PFSs, HFSs, and NSs. The SVNAHP is comprised of the following steps [22]:

Step 1. Drawing an AHP hierarchy for the problem: In this step, the problem is modeled as a hierarchy comprised of objectives, FMs, and evaluation Factors.

Step 2. Forming the pairwise comparison matrix: This step involves building a pairwise comparison matrix by asking experts to make pairwise comparisons between elements in each row of the plotted hierarchy.

Step 3. Determining the weights of experts: Before aggregating the matrices obtained from multiple experts, it is necessary to determine how much important the inputs of each expert are relative to others. Supposing that each expert (e) is evaluated in terms of a NN such as

$E_k = T_k, I_k, F_k$, the weight of experts is obtained by using Eq. (11) [15].

$$w_k = \frac{1 - \sqrt{\frac{\{(1 - T_k(x))^2, (I_k(x))^2, (F_k(x))^2\}}{3}}}{\sum_{k=1}^e \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{\{(1 - T_k(x))^2, (I_k(x))^2, (F_k(x))^2\}}{3}} \right)}, \text{ and } \sum_{k=1}^e w_k = 1 \tag{11}$$

Step 4. Forming the aggregated pairwise comparison matrix (X): In this step, pairwise comparison matrices are aggregated using the SVN weighted average operator (SVNWAO) as follows in Eq. (12) [15].

$$\begin{aligned}
 SVNWAO_w(d_{ij}^1, d_{ij}^2, \dots, d_{ij}^r) = \\
 w_1 d_{ij}^1 \oplus w_2 d_{ij}^2 \oplus \dots \oplus w_k d_{ij}^r = \\
 1 - \prod_{p=1}^r (1 - T_{ij}^{rp})^{w_k}, \prod_{p=1}^r (I_{ij}^{rp})^{w_k}, \prod_{p=1}^r (F_{ij}^{rp})^{w_k}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{12}$$

The aggregated pairwise comparison matrix is then formed as follows in Eq. (13):

$$X = (x_{ij})_{m \times n} = \langle T_{ij}, I_{ij}, F_{ij} \rangle_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{pmatrix}
 \tag{13}$$

Where x_{ij} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n$) denotes SVN values.

Step 5. De-neutrosophication of NNs and their conversion to crisp values using the score function (Eq. (10)): Supposing S is a score matrix written as Eq. (14), we have:

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & \dots & S_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ S_{m1} & \dots & S_{mn} \end{pmatrix}
 \tag{14}$$

where $S_{ij} = S(x_{ij})$ is the score of x_{ij} .

Step 6. Normalizing the score matrix and forming the matrix \bar{S} as Eq. (15).

$$\bar{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11} & \dots & \bar{S}_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \bar{S}_{m1} & \dots & \bar{S}_{mn} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{S}_{ij} = S_{ij} / \sum_{j=1}^3 S_{ij}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = O, S, D)
 \tag{15}$$

Step 7. Computing the weights of Factor by using Eq. (16).

$$w_j = \sum_{j=1}^3 \bar{S}_{ij} / 3, \quad j = O, S, D
 \tag{16}$$

2.3. Steps of SVNVIKOR

The method known as VIKOR was developed by Opricovic in 1998. Later, this method was combined with the FS theory [23] and its extensions including TFSs, SFSs, IVFSs, IT2FSs, IFSs, IVIFSs, HFSs, PFSs and NSs. SVNVIKOR consists of the following steps [24, 25]:

Step 8. Forming decision matrices: In this step, a decision matrix is formed for each expert based on FMs and evaluation Factors.

Step 9. Forming the aggregated decision matrix: After weighting the experts (Eq. (11)), the aggregated decision matrix is obtained by using Eq. (12).

Step 10. Obtaining the weighted SVN matrix: Supposing that K is the aggregated decision matrix and W is the criteria weight matrix obtained from SVNAHP, the weighted SVN matrix is obtained by using Eq. (17). Supposing that $K = k_{ij}^*$, one can write:

$$K^* = K \otimes W \tag{17}$$

Where $k_{ij}^* = w_j \otimes k_{ij} = (T_{ij}^W, I_{ij}^W, F_{ij}^W)$.

Also, the SVN aggregated matrix is given by using Eq. (18):

$$KK^* = \begin{pmatrix} kw_{11} & \dots & kw_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ kw_{m1} & \dots & kw_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \tag{18}$$

Step 11. Determining the positive and negative ideals (best and worst point among feasible solutions) for each criterion: Here, the classic VIKOR model is extended to SVNSs, and the positive ideal W_j^+ and the negative ideal W_j^- for all Factors $\beta_j (j = O, S, D)$ are obtained by using Eq. (19):

$$\begin{aligned} T_j^{W+} &= \left\{ \left(\max_i T_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_1 \right), \left(\min_i T_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_2 \right) \right\}, \\ I_j^{W+} &= \left\{ \left(\min_i I_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_1 \right), \left(\max_i I_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_2 \right) \right\}, \\ F_j^{W+} &= \left\{ \left(\min_i F_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_1 \right), \left(\max_i F_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_2 \right) \right\}, \\ T_j^{W-} &= \left\{ \left(\min_i T_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_1 \right), \left(\max_i T_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_2 \right) \right\}, \\ I_j^{W-} &= \left\{ \left(\max_i I_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_1 \right), \left(\min_i I_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_2 \right) \right\}, \\ F_j^{W-} &= \left\{ \left(\max_i F_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_1 \right), \left(\min_i F_{ij}^W \mid j \in G_2 \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

where G_1 is the set of benefit Factor and G_2 is the set of damage Factor.

W_j^+ and W_j^- for all Factors can be written by using Eq. (20):

$$W_j^+ = \langle T_{ij}^{W^+}, I_{ij}^{W^+}, F_{ij}^{W^+} \rangle, W_j^- = \langle T_{ij}^{W^-}, I_{ij}^{W^-}, F_{ij}^{W^-} \rangle, (j = O, S, D) \tag{20}$$

Step 12. Computing S_i and R_i for $(i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$: The values of S_i and R_i for each FMs are obtained by using Eqs. (21-22):

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \frac{\|W_j^+ - W_{ij}\|}{\|W_j^+ - W_j^-\|}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, m) \tag{21}$$

$$R_i = \max_j w_j \frac{\|W_j^+ - W_{ij}\|}{\|W_j^+ - W_j^-\|}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, m) \tag{22}$$

In these equations, w_j is the weight of Factor j . Having W_j^+ and W_j^- and the Hamming distance, the SVN versions of S_i and R_i are obtained by using Eqs. (23-24).

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \frac{|T_j^{W^+} - T_{ij}^W| + |I_j^{W^+} - I_{ij}^W| + |F_j^{W^+} - F_{ij}^W|}{|T_j^{W^+} - T_j^{W^-}| + |I_j^{W^+} - I_j^{W^-}| + |F_j^{W^+} - F_j^{W^-}|}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, m) \tag{23}$$

$$R_i = \max_j w_j \frac{|T_j^{W^+} - T_{ij}^W| + |I_j^{W^+} - I_{ij}^W| + |F_j^{W^+} - F_{ij}^W|}{|T_j^{W^+} - T_j^{W^-}| + |I_j^{W^+} - I_j^{W^-}| + |F_j^{W^+} - F_j^{W^-}|}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, m) \tag{24}$$

Step 13. Computing Q_i : Q_i is obtained Factor by using Eq. (25):

$$Q_i = \gamma \left[\frac{S_i - S^+}{S^- - S^+} \right] + (1 - \gamma) \left[\frac{R_i - R^+}{R^- - R^+} \right], (i = 1, 2, \dots, m) \tag{25}$$

Where $S^+ = \min_i S_i$, $S^- = \max_i S_i$, $R^+ = \min_i R_i$, $R^- = \max_i R_i$, γ is the weight of the strategy of maximum group utility. In this study, γ was considered to be 0.9.

Step 14. Ranking FMs: In this step, the FMs FM_1, FM_2, \dots, FM_m are ranked in ascending order of their R_i , S_i , and Q_i values.

The FM with the lowest Q value ($FM_{i(1)}$) is said to be a compromise solution if the following two conditions are satisfied:

Condition 1. Acceptable advantage:

$$Q_{i2} - Q_{i1} \geq \frac{1}{m-1}$$

Where FM_{i2} is the second-ranking FM in terms of Q value and m is the number of FMs.

Condition 2. Acceptable stability in decision-making:

The $FM_{i(1)}$ must also be the highest-ranked $FM_{i(1)}$ in terms of S or R . This compromise solution is stable when it is the strategy of maximum group utility (*when $\gamma > 0.5$ is needed*), or is selected by consensus ($\gamma \approx 0.5$) or voting with veto ($\gamma < 0.5$).

If one of the above conditions is not met, then a set of compromise solutions is formed from either:

- FMs FM_{i1} and FM_{i2} if only Condition 2 is not satisfied or
- FMs $FM_{i(1)}, FM_{i(2)}, \dots, FM_{i(u)}$ if Condition 1 is not satisfied.

$FM_{i(u)}$ is determined by the relation $Q_{i(u)} - Q_{i(1)} < \frac{1}{m-1}$ for maximum u (these alternatives are in close positions).

3. Proposed approach

NSs are a generalized version of classical, FSs, and IFSs, which have been developed for better handling of uncertainty, inconsistency, and incompleteness of information in real-world problems by considering three aspects of decision-making called T, I, and F. Therefore, the introduction of NSs to VIKOR and AHP can lead to even better control over ambiguity and uncertainty compared to when these methods are integrated with FSs or IFSs. This paper presents a new FMEA developed by combining VIKOR and AHP under the SVNS framework to address the shortcomings of traditional FMEA in the area of risk prioritization, and also presents the results of using the approach in the assessment of supply chain sustainability risks for the mining company ICIOC (Bafgh, Iran). In a world where supply chain network design plays a critical role in business performance and competitiveness of companies [26]. increasing globalization, outsourcing, and market competition is constantly creating new supply chain management challenges, and companies that compete in global markets are under constant pressure to actively integrate sustainability criteria into their supply chain processes to counter the adverse social and environmental impacts of their business activities [27]. the concept of supply chain sustainability is increasingly seen as a great opportunity for cost-saving and a necessity for the long-term profitability of businesses. However, this attitude

also generates some risks for companies as it makes their supply chains more sensitive to natural disasters or crises taking place across the globe. Today, companies that set up their own supply chains are more than ever exposed to such risks. Supply chain risk, along with supply chain disruption, is among the terms that the media and stakeholders constantly use in their assessment of the damage done to supply chains and jobs in this sector. Risks can originate from internal or external sources, i.e. factors that can affect the sustainability of the business environment and operational procedures. In the context of supply chains, risk could be any event outside one’s expectations and control that causes disruption in the natural flow of materials and information across the supply chain and imposes extra costs on its stakeholders [28]. An outline of the proposed approach is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Proposed approach

4. Case study: risk assessment in Bafgh iron ore mine

To demonstrate To illustrate how the proposed approach can be applied, it was used in a case study involving the risk assessment of the Bafgh iron ore mine. Provided in the following is a step-by-step description of how SVNAHP-SVNVIKOR-based FMEA was implemented in this risk assessment.

Phase 1. Identification of risk items

First, the literature on the subject and similar areas [29-31] were reviewed to identify a set of initial risk items. Then, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted with four experts of ICIOC with at least 20 years' experience of working in the business or the company's supply chain, who narrowed down these initial items to 21 final risk items listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Supply chain sustainability risks of ICIOC

Risk Dimension	Failure mode	Risk item description
Social	FM1	Unhealthy and unsafe work environment
	FM2	Failure to fulfill social commitments
	FM3	Discrimination (race, gender, religion, disability, age, political views)
	FM4	
	FM5	Social instability
	FM6	Local false inflation
	FM7	Long work hours (work-life imbalance)
	FM8	Labor exploitation (no contract, no insurance)
	FM9	Groundwater drawdown and pollution
Environmental	FM10	Natural disasters (e.g. storms, floods, etc.)
	FM11	Environmental pollution (air, water, soil)
	FM12	Waste accumulation
	FM13	Inefficient resource utilization
	FM14	Decreased ore grade
	FM15	Receivable impairment
Economic	FM16	Sale of crude ore
	FM17	Inaccessibility and irreplaceability of reserves and resources
	FM18	Lack of control over operating costs
	FM19	Sanctions
	FM20	Shrinking market share
	FM21	Inflation and exchange rate changes
		Price and cost fluctuations

Phase 2. Weighting of failure factors with SVNAHP

Step 1. The subject's hierarchical model was drawn with three risk factors (O, S, and D) and 21 risk items.

Step 2. The pairwise comparison matrix was designed for determining the weights of factors O, S, and D and distributed among the experts. In this step, pairwise comparisons were performed using linguistic terms and SVNNs given in Table 2.

Table 2. SVN scale used for pairwise comparisons [22]

Linguistic term	NS	Linguistic term	Reciprocal NS
Extremely Highly Preferred	(0.90, 0.10, 0.10)	Mildly Lowly Preferred	(0.10, 0.90, 0.90)
Extremely Preferred	(0.85, 0.20, 0.15)	Mildly Preferred	(0.15, 0.80, 0.85)
Very Strongly to Extremely Preferred	(0.80, 0.25, 0.20)	Mildly preferred to Very Lowly Preferred	(0.20, 0.75, 0.80)
Very Strongly Preferred	(0.75, 0.25, 0.25)	Very Lowly Preferred	(0.25, 0.75, 0.75)
Strongly Preferred	(0.70, 0.30, 0.30)	Lowly Preferred	(0.30, 0.70, 0.70)
Moderately Highly to Strongly Preferred	(0.65, 0.30, 0.35)	Moderately Lowly Preferred to Lowly Preferred	(0.35, 0.70, 0.65)
Moderately Highly Preferred	(0.60, 0.35, 0.40)	Moderately Lowly Preferred	(0.40, 0.65, 0.60)
Equally to Moderately Preferred	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)	Moderately to Equally Preferred	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)
Equally Preferred	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	Equally Preferred	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)

The resulting pairwise comparison matrix is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Pairwise comparison matrix

Factors	E1			Factors	E2		
	O	S	D		O	S	D
O	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.60, 0.35, 0.40)	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)	O	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)	(0.40, 0.65, 0.60)
S	(0.40, 0.65, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.60, 0.35, 0.40)	S	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)
D	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)	(0.40, 0.65, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	D	(0.60, 0.35, 0.40)	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)
Factors	E3			Factors	E4		
	O	S	D		O	S	D
O	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.35, 0.70, 0.65)	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)	O	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)
S	(0.65, 0.30, 0.35)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)	S	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.60, 0.35, 0.40)
D	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)	(0.45, 0.60, 0.55)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)	D	(0.55, 0.40, 0.45)	(0.40, 0.65, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)

Step 3. The weights of experts were determined using linguistic terms and NNs given in Table 4.

Table 4. Linguistic terms and their corresponding SVNns for expert weighting [15]

Linguistic term	SVNN (T_{ij}, I_{ij}, F_{ij})
Very Important (VI)	(0.9, 0.10, 0.10)
Important (I)	(0.80, 0.20, 0.15)
Medium (M)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.45)
Unimportant (U)	(0.35, 0.60, 0.70)
Very Unimportant (VU)	(0.10, 0.80, 0.90)

Each expert was given a code (VI, I, M, and U) in the SVN environment. The weights determined by Eq. (11) are provided below:

$$w_1 = 0.165, w_2 = 0.263, w_3 = 0.31, w_4 = 0.263$$

Step 4. After determining the weights of experts, the process continues by obtaining the neutrosophic aggregated decision matrix using Eq. (12). The resulting matrix is given in Table 5.

Table 5. Aggregated pairwise comparison matrix

Factors	O	S	D
O	(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)	(0.45, 0.576, 0.55)	(0.471, 0.54, 0.529)
S	(0.563, 0.396, 0.437)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)	(0.572, 0.378, 0.428)
D	(0.536, 0.438, 0.464)	(0.429, 0.621, 0.571)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)

Step 5. The neutrosophic aggregated decision matrix was converted to crisp values using the score function (Eq. (14)). The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Conversion of aggregated decision matrix into crisp values

Factors	O	S	D
O	0.5	0.437	0.465
S	0.584	0.5	0.597
D	0.549	0.404	0.5

Step 6. The aggregated decision matrix was normalized by using the Saaty norm (Eq. (15)). The resulting normalized matrix is provided in Table 7.

Table 7. Normalized matrix

Factors	O	S	D
O	0.306	0.326	0.298
S	0.357	0.373	0.382
D	0.336	0.301	0.32

Step 7. The weights of risk factors, which were obtained from Eq. (16), are listed in Table 8.

Table 8. Weights of risk factors

Factors	O	S	D
W	0.31	0.371	0.319

Phase 3. Ranking of risk items using SVNVIKOR

Step 8. The decision matrix was designed based on the determined risk factors and items and distributed among the experts. In this step, risk item assessments were performed using linguistic terms and SVNNs given in Table 9.

Table 9. Linguistic terms and SVNNs used in the assessment of risk items [15]

Linguistic term	SVNN (T_{ij}, I_{ij}, F_{ij})
Extremely high (EH)	(1.00, 0.00, 0.00)
Very high (VH)	(0.90, 0.10, 0.05)
High (H)	(0.80, 0.20, 0.15)
Medium high (MH)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.30)
Medium (M)	(0.50, 0.50, 0.45)
Medium low (ML)	(0.35, 0.65, 0.60)
Low (L)	(0.20, 0.75, 0.80)
Very low (VL)	(0.10, 0.85, 0.90)
Extremely low (EL)	(0.05, 0.90, 0.95)

The results are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Assessment of risk items based on SVNNs

Items	E1			Items	E2		
	O	S	D		O	S	D
FM1	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	FM1	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM2	(0.35, 0.65, 0.6)	(0.2, 0.75, 0.8)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM2	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM3	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM3	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM4	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM4	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM5	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM5	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM6	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM6	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM7	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM7	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)
FM8	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.35, 0.65, 0.6)	FM8	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM9	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM9	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM10	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.2, 0.75, 0.8)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM10	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM11	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM11	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM12	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM12	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM13	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM13	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM14	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM14	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM15	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM15	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)

FM16	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM16	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)
FM17	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	FM17	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM18	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM18	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM19	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM19	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM20	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM20	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM21	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM21	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)

Items	E3			Items	E4		
	O	S	D		O	S	D
FM1	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM1	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.35, 0.65, 0.6)
FM2	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM2	(0.2, 0.75, 0.8)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM3	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM3	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM4	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	FM4	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM5	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM5	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM6	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM6	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM7	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM7	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)
FM8	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM8	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM9	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM9	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM10	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM10	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM11	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM11	(0.35, 0.65, 0.6)	(0.2, 0.75, 0.8)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)
FM12	(0.35, 0.65, 0.6)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM12	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM13	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM13	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM14	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM14	(0.35, 0.65, 0.6)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM15	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM15	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM16	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM16	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)
FM17	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM17	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM18	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM18	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM19	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	FM19	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)
FM20	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	FM20	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)
FM21	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	FM21	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.45)

Step 9. The neutrosophic aggregated decision matrix was obtained from Eq. (12). This matrix is given in Table 11.

Table 11. neutrosophic aggregated decision matrix

Items	O	S	D
FM1	(0.816, 0.184, 0.118)	(0.71, 0.291, 0.236)	(0.62, 0.377, 0.321)
FM2	(0.471, 0.52, 0.484)	(0.68, 0.316, 0.264)	(0.79, 0.212, 0.151)
FM3	(0.704, 0.296, 0.225)	(0.67, 0.327, 0.253)	(0.57, 0.428, 0.388)
FM4	(0.704, 0.296, 0.24)	(0.73, 0.267, 0.2)	(0.61, 0.391, 0.34)
FM5	(0.851, 0.149, 0.094)	(0.83, 0.167, 0.107)	(0.78, 0.217, 0.154)
FM6	(0.662, 0.338, 0.281)	(0.84, 0.162, 0.101)	(0.82, 0.181, 0.117)
FM7	(0.763, 0.237, 0.172)	(0.65, 0.352, 0.297)	(0.54, 0.461, 0.405)
FM8	(0.788, 0.212, 0.151)	(0.76, 0.239, 0.171)	(0.8, 0.196, 0.134)
FM9	(0.576, 0.424, 0.372)	(0.79, 0.205, 0.143)	(0.7, 0.302, 0.227)
FM10	(0.715, 0.285, 0.223)	(0.67, 0.325, 0.251)	(0.76, 0.237, 0.172)
FM11	(0.676, 0.324, 0.268)	(0.65, 0.344, 0.275)	(0.81, 0.189, 0.125)
FM12	(0.645, 0.355, 0.276)	(0.84, 0.161, 0.107)	(0.65, 0.35, 0.3)
FM13	(0.788, 0.212, 0.151)	(0.73, 0.266, 0.211)	(0.75, 0.246, 0.186)
FM14	(0.676, 0.324, 0.268)	(0.7, 0.302, 0.235)	(0.83, 0.172, 0.113)
FM15	(0.734, 0.266, 0.211)	(0.79, 0.212, 0.151)	(0.87, 0.134, 0.08)
FM16	(0.802, 0.198, 0.139)	(0.84, 0.165, 0.099)	(0.73, 0.27, 0.207)
FM17	(0.775, 0.225, 0.155)	(0.82, 0.183, 0.126)	(0.81, 0.194, 0.135)
FM18	(0.8, 0.2, 0.15)	(0.86, 0.139, 0.08)	(0.88, 0.12, 0.067)
FM19	(0.746, 0.254, 0.202)	(0.8, 0.198, 0.139)	(0.85, 0.149, 0.094)
FM20	(0.748, 0.252, 0.184)	(0.86, 0.144, 0.089)	(0.85, 0.147, 0.087)
FM21	(0.876, 0.124, 0.07)	(0.87, 0.134, 0.08)	(0.74, 0.261, 0.192)

Step 10. The weighted SVN matrix obtained in this step using Eq. (17) is shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Weighted SVN matrix

Items	O	S	D
FM1	(0.408, 0.592, 0.516)	(0.367, 0.633, 0.586)	(0.268, 0.732, 0.696)
FM2	(0.179, 0.817, 0.799)	(0.345, 0.653, 0.61)	(0.391, 0.609, 0.547)
FM3	(0.314, 0.686, 0.63)	(0.339, 0.661, 0.6)	(0.233, 0.763, 0.739)
FM4	(0.314, 0.686, 0.642)	(0.387, 0.613, 0.551)	(0.259, 0.741, 0.709)
FM5	(0.446, 0.554, 0.48)	(0.485, 0.515, 0.436)	(0.386, 0.614, 0.55)
FM6	(0.286, 0.714, 0.675)	(0.491, 0.509, 0.427)	(0.42, 0.58, 0.504)
FM7	(0.36, 0.64, 0.58)	(0.321, 0.679, 0.638)	(0.219, 0.781, 0.749)
FM8	(0.382, 0.618, 0.557)	(0.412, 0.588, 0.519)	(0.406, 0.594, 0.527)
FM9	(0.234, 0.766, 0.736)	(0.444, 0.556, 0.486)	(0.318, 0.682, 0.623)
FM10	(0.323, 0.677, 0.628)	(0.338, 0.659, 0.599)	(0.368, 0.632, 0.57)
FM11	(0.295, 0.705, 0.665)	(0.323, 0.673, 0.619)	(0.412, 0.588, 0.515)
FM12	(0.275, 0.725, 0.671)	(0.492, 0.508, 0.436)	(0.285, 0.715, 0.681)
FM13	(0.382, 0.618, 0.557)	(0.388, 0.612, 0.561)	(0.361, 0.639, 0.585)
FM14	(0.295, 0.705, 0.665)	(0.359, 0.641, 0.584)	(0.43, 0.57, 0.498)
FM15	(0.337, 0.663, 0.617)	(0.438, 0.562, 0.496)	(0.473, 0.527, 0.447)
FM16	(0.395, 0.605, 0.543)	(0.488, 0.512, 0.424)	(0.342, 0.658, 0.605)
FM17	(0.37, 0.63, 0.561)	(0.468, 0.532, 0.464)	(0.408, 0.592, 0.527)
FM18	(0.393, 0.607, 0.555)	(0.519, 0.481, 0.392)	(0.492, 0.508, 0.421)
FM19	(0.346, 0.654, 0.609)	(0.451, 0.549, 0.481)	(0.456, 0.544, 0.47)
FM20	(0.348, 0.652, 0.592)	(0.513, 0.487, 0.408)	(0.457, 0.543, 0.459)
FM21	(0.477, 0.523, 0.439)	(0.525, 0.475, 0.392)	(0.349, 0.651, 0.59)

Step 11. The positive and negative ideals for each risk item were determined by using Eq. (19). The results are provided in Table 13.

Table 13. Positive and negative ideals for risk items

	O	S	D
W_j^+	(0.477, 0.523, 0.439)	(0.525, 0.475, 0.392)	(0.492, 0.508, 0.421)
W_j^-	(0.179, 0.817, 0.799)	(0.321, 0.679, 0.638)	(0.219, 0.781, 0.749)

Steps 12, 13, and 14. R_i , S_i and Q_i values were computed by using Eqs. (23-25) and the FMs were ranked accordingly. The resulting rankings are given in Table 14.

Table 14. The values of S_i , R_i and Q_i ranking of FMs

Items	S_i	R_i	Q_i	Ranking
Price and cost fluctuations	0.166	0.166	0.111	2
Inflation and exchange rate changes	0.196	0.134	0.136	2
Long work hours (work-life imbalance)	0.342	0.202	0.345	9
Labor exploitation (no contract, no insurance)	0.812	0.371	1	21
Sanctions	0.099	0.093	0	1
Failure to fulfill social commitments	0.756	0.327	0.914	19
Discrimination (race, gender, religion, disability, age, political views)	0.801	0.329	0.971	19
Natural disasters (e.g. storms, floods, etc.)	0.601	0.255	0.692	13
Lack of control over operating costs	0.315	0.109	0.278	5
Inaccessibility and irreplaceability of reserves and resources	0.324	0.177	0.314	5
Inefficient resource utilization	0.517	0.246	0.582	11
Local false inflation	0.228	0.124	0.173	4
Waste accumulation	0.641	0.356	0.778	15
Decreased ore grade	0.506	0.251	0.571	11
Environmental pollution (air, water, soil)	0.635	0.327	0.76	15

Social instability	0.694	0.275	0.816	18
Sale of crude ore	0.33	0.158	0.315	5
Groundwater drawdown and pollution	0.402	0.2	0.42	10
Receivable impairment	0.563	0.298	0.659	13
Shrinking market share	0.319	0.141	0.294	5
Unhealthy and unsafe work environment	0.623	0.289	0.732	15

Phase 4. Sensitivity analysis

In this study, a sensitivity analysis was performed to gain better insight into the accuracy, stability, and validity of the proposed model. A sensitivity analysis can also provide highly useful information about the uncertainty of experts. Here, in addition to the proposed model, a classic VIKOR model was also used for ranking in order to see the change in the ranking of risk items.

While the purpose of SVNVIKOR was to rank the obtained risk items, the purpose of classic VIKOR was to determine how much the method changes the ranking of risk items. The results of the ranking of risk items using the classic VIKOR model are presented in Table 15. The results showed a high degree of similarity between the rankings obtained from the proposed method and the classic VIKOR model.

Table 15. Ranking of risk items divided by the method

Failure mode	Items	Current study	Method 1
FM21	Price and cost fluctuations	2	2
FM20	Inflation and exchange rate changes	2	2
FM6	Long work hours (work-life imbalance)	9	8
FM7	Labor exploitation (no contract, no insurance)	21	21
FM18	Sanctions	1	1
FM2	Failure to fulfill social commitments	19	19
FM3	Discrimination (race, gender, religion, disability, age, political views)	19	19
FM9	Natural disasters (e.g. storms, floods, etc.)	13	13
FM17	Lack of control over operating costs	5	5
FM16	Inaccessibility and irreplaceability of reserves and resources	5	5
FM12	Inefficient resource utilization	11	11
FM5	Local false inflation	4	2
FM11	Waste accumulation	15	15
FM13	Decreased ore grade	11	11
FM10	Environmental pollution (air, water, soil)	15	15
FM4	Social instability	18	18
FM15	Sale of crude ore	5	8
FM8	Groundwater drawdown and pollution	10	10
FM14	Receivable impairment	13	13
FM19	Shrinking market share	5	5
FM1	Unhealthy and unsafe work environment	15	15

5. Conclusions and final remarks

Among the wide variety of risk assessment methods developed over the years, FMEA is still one of the strongest in terms of the ability to detect and assess risk items. It has been shown that this method can be used in combination with other methods to provide a better assessment of risks in different areas. While FSs and IFSs tend to perform very well in dealing with uncertainty in real-world problems, they also have their own shortcomings, which make NSs a more suitable option for integration with FMEA. Using the concept of NSs, real-world multi-criteria decision problems can be modeled and solved with due attention to T, I, and F of judgments. Therefore, in the present paper, this concept was used to enhance FMEA. To test the proposed model, it was used to

rank the supply chain sustainability risk items of the mining company ICIOC (Bafgh, Iran) based on expert opinions. In the proposed approach, first, experts are weighted by the use of linguistic terms and SVNNSs, then the decision matrices formed from expert opinions are aggregated to weight risk parameters, and finally, SVNVIKOR is used to rank risk items. The results of the study showed that “sanctions”, “price and cost fluctuations”, and “inflation and exchange rate changes” are the most critical risks threatening the success of ICIOC.

In this study, sanctions were found to be the most important risk item originating from politics. The groundwork for the use of economic sanctions as a geopolitical tool was laid after the Cold War and since then they have been increasingly employed for such purposes. While economic sanctions can be an attractive political tool, their effectiveness is debatable. It has been suggested that sanctions often lead to more authoritarianism, increased government repression, poor governance, public health deterioration, widespread poverty, and higher levels of income inequality in targeted countries. Import-export sanctions tend to be most effective in the short term, when they disrupt the trade patterns of the targeted country, but they lose effectiveness over time as the targeted country finds new trading partners and learns how to evade them [32]. Nevertheless, sanctions often have a significant negative impact on the profitability of companies operating in the targeted countries.

Another critical risk identified in this study was the risk of price and cost fluctuations. Pricing is one of the main tools that a company has at its disposal to improve its revenue, and also one of the most important determinants of demand size [33]. Price fluctuations can generally be defined as an increase or decrease in the price of goods, materials, and services in the market. Prices of products and services tend to fluctuate dynamically with supply-demand variations in the market. Short-term fluctuations often have economic causes. Upward price fluctuations may result in reduced production, leading to a larger trade deficit, currency devaluation, high inflation, and reduced economic activity [34]. Therefore, the government and all stakeholders must work together to mitigate the negative impact of this phenomenon on the economy.

Another important risk identified in this study was the risk of inflation and exchange rate changes. It has been shown that prices may react differently to major changes in exchange rates, and currency devaluation may cause an asymmetric reaction to price increases. While the total asset value of a company is influenced by many external factors, macroeconomic factors, i.e. inflation and exchange rate, play a bold role in this regard. Inflation, defined as a constant increase in the price of goods and services, is certainly one of the primary concerns of any government, as it is viewed as a measure of the country’s economic performance. Exchange rate pass-through refers to the sustained interaction between currency exchange rate and inflation whereby any change in one affects the other and vice versa. Developing economies tend to have stronger exchange rate and inflation fluctuations, including for basic commodities, and show a stronger relationship between public debt and policy interest rates [35].

The findings of this study can be a stepping stone for developing targeted strategies and plans for continuous enhancement of risk assessments and the insights they provide to managers and decision-makers. Furthermore, the combination of SVNAHP and SVNVIKOR can provide a strong platform for dealing with the ambiguities that are prevalent in business environments. The proposed approach allows for more accurate and realistic decision-making under such circumstances. Future studies are recommended to integrate different versions of FSs, including PFSs, IT2FSs and HFSs into risk assessments and compare their results with the outputs of the proposed method. Also, FMEA can be combined with other decision-making techniques such as AHP and TOPSIS in a SVN environment. Finally, it can be said that the proposed approach can be used in different industries.

In this article, the abbreviations are as described in Table (16).

Table 16. Abbreviations/Nomenclatures/Symbols

Terms	Abbreviations
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Failure Modes and Effect Analysis	FMEA
single-valued neutrosophic	SVN
Analytic Hierarchy Process	AHP
Vlsekriterijumska Optimizacija I Kompromisno Resenje	VIKOR
single-valued neutrosophic version of AHP	SVNAHP
single-valued neutrosophic version of VIKOR	SVNVIKOR
Iran Central Iron Ore Co	ICIOC
Multi-Criteria Decision Making	MCDM
Risk Priority Number	RPN
Single-valued neutrosophic weighted average operator	SVNWAO
Occurrence	O
Severity	S
Detection	D
Single-valued neutrosophic set	SVNS
truth	T
indeterminacy	I
falsity	F
single-valued neutrosophic number	SVNN
Single-Valued Neutrosophic set	SVNS
Failure modes	FMs
fuzzy set	FS
triangular fuzzy sets	TFSs
triangular interval-valued fuzzy sets	TIVFSs
interval type 2 fuzzy sets	IT2FSs
Pythagorean fuzzy sets	PFSs
gray fuzzy sets	GFSs
intuitionistic fuzzy sets	IFSs
interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets	IVIFSs
hesitant fuzzy sets	HFSs
triangular interval type-2 fuzzy	TIT2F
spherical fuzzy sets	SFSs
Neutrosophic numbers	NNs

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